

Tectonic faulting investigation of the Southern part of Mt. Carmel using integrated geophysical techniques

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The margins of Israel have been traditionally divided into a southern passive margin and an active northern one. Additionally, the Carmel fault which borders Mt. Carmel is understood to have separated the Southern and Northern margins of Israel. However, there has been no clear understanding as to whether the Carmel fault within the Southern margin of Israel is continuous to the coast or terminated as elucidated by different published maps of active or potentially active faults in Israel which have shown the presence, as well as the absence of faults branching from the Carmel fault towards the coast. Past studies have made use of the preservation of fossils, seismicity records, and ancient physical structures to determine the stability/instability of the area, but little to no work has been carried out to assess tectonic activity adjacent to Mt. Carmel to the south and therefore, nothing is known about this area. This study sets out to determine the continuity of the southern branches of the Carmel fault onshore, buried faults, and the stability/instability of the faulted branches in the Southern margin of Israel through the integration, analyses, and interpretation of Ground Penetration Radar (GPR) and Frequency domain electromagnetic method (FD-EM) which will reveal the artifacts embedded within the study area. This study is expected to give an awareness of the continuity or truncation of the southern branch of the Carmel fault towards the land, buried faults, and hazards associated with active fault margins which can be used as a guide to protect lives and properties around the study area.